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Postmodern Influences On *Egwu Otu* Music Performances

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ABSTRACT

Egwu otu dance music is an envious traditional music of the Ogba community. It is the oldest and commonest musical culture of the Omoku clan in Ogba community. Over eight decades ago, the membership of *Egwu Otu* dance music was restricted to only the male folks of the community. Currently, the music is becoming popular as a result of postmodernic influences. There are some innovations introduced by some of the groups, in terms of the membership, songs, mode of operations, uniformity and others. The impact of these innovations on the groups has not been ascertained. The aim of this study is to ascertain the level of postmodernic influence on *Egwu otu* music, analyze its implication on the music and entire community and recommend ways of cushioning the influence. The study will adopt participants' observation and interview as a method of data collection. The subjects of the study are selected members of *Egwu Otu* dance music group. Recommendations and conclusions will be made using the findings from the study.

Keywords: postmodernic, performances, implications, *Egwu Otu*, music

INTRODUCTION

Traditional music undoubtedly is one of the most creative arts of African societies. Hence Okafor (1974) opines that "Music is unquestionably the most widely practiced of the traditional arts in Nigeria. At any time of night or day, somewhere in the land, some music is being made" (105). Thus indigenous music of the African has remained a significant tool for general expression and the application of the cultural values and conducts of their various communities. Succinctly, Okafor (2005) states, "In the African culture, music is an entirety rather than a mere mental creation or conception. It reflects and interprets the man in a specific environment and is often the key, which opens the gate to spiritual, mental, emotional, psychological, social and mystic realms" (88). Based on the back drop of the above definition, it is quite explicit the role which African music play in our society. The man as a being is interwoven with music within his environment and as such this paves way to other achievements that are essential to man. Onyeji and Onyeji (2011) assert that "African music may be described as the specific musical arts creations of indigenous African societies with which they celebrate and conduct their social and cultural events and in which various aspects of their cultural lives are woven, documented and exhibited when needed" (19). Conversely, Ofili (2021) opines that "traditional music is one of the major Art forms that

have showcased over centuries by different tribes and communities in Nigeria to preserve culture, history, legends and traditions” (116).

Egwu otu (age grade) dance music is a traditional musical culture of the Omoku community in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Fakeye & Ogunbona (2014) define culture as “the totality of the way of life evolved by a people in their attempt to meet the challenge of living in their environment which gives order and meaning to their social, political, economic aesthetic and religious norms and mode of organization. Thus, distinguishing a group of people from their neighbors” (83). In line with this definition, Aziza in Loko (2014) opines that, culture is “the totality of the pattern of a particular group of a people consisting of their greeting habits, dressing, social norms and taboos, food, song and dance patterns, rites of passage from birth through marriage to death, traditional occupations, religion as well as philosophical beliefs” (78). The music comprises traditional songs, dance and instrumentation. *Egwu otu* dance music is the most accessible and significant musical activity of the Omoku community in Ogba land. Apparently, over decades, the music has served as means of propagating the cultural identity, norms, values, and legends of the people of Omoku community which has resulted to a very high level of development in the community. Ibekwe in Ofili (2021) notes that “culture gives identity to a nation, and it is based on this (culture) that a nation’s development is anchored” (78).

Consequently, *Egwu otu* music has been in existence for over a decade. These changes as expressed by Ofili “was as a result of Christianity, modernity, cultism and other external influences” (116). These aforementioned factors led to a serious decline in the membership of various age grade groups in Omoku community which of course affected most of their activities. However, in recent times, the envious musical culture is gaining popularity though with few innovations as a result of postmodernic ideas and activities embraced by the members of the various groups.

This discourse will delve into the historic perspective of *Egwu otu* music from the past to the present. It will also look at the significance of this music to the Omoku community, and of course, the implications of postmodernic ideas on *Egwu otu* musical activities.

Problem of the study

Historically, *Egwu otu* music performance was restricted to the male folks of the community. Only married men or men who have attained marriageable age were eligible to bring in their spouses or fiancés during the last musical activity of the year. In recent times, some women folks of the community were admitted into the various age grades. In other words, some of the women registered as members in their various age grades. Furthermore, unmarried and younger men who have not also attained marriageable age were also competing with the married men by having their female friends as companion to their age grades during the last musical event of the year. These and few other issues are the major problems of this study.

Purpose of the study

With respect to the aforementioned problems of the study, the objectives of the study will include;

- i. Find out the reason the women folks of the community are being admitted as members of *Egwu otu* dance music which is meant for the men folks of the community,
- ii. Ascertain the reason the younger and unmarried men of the community took their female friends to participate during the last musical event which was meant for married men and those who have attained marriageable ages.
- iii. Examine the reason the younger men folks of *Egwu otu* process during the event on the same day as the older men folks,
- iv. X-ray the general implications of the aforementioned postmodernic activities on *Egwu otu* musical culture of Omoku community.

History of *Egwu otu*

For clarity purpose, before delving into the history of *Egwu otu* music, a brief history of Ogba community whose musical culture is the discourse will be discussed will be looked into. Ogba is a community in the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni (ONELGA) Local Government Area of Rivers State. Historically, as expressed by Ella (2010), the Ogba are originally from Benin in the present Edo state of Nigeria. The Bini asserts that, they came all the way from Ehem (Ancient Egypt) and found a more secured place in this part of the world after a short stay in Sudan. They settled at Ife which Benin people call Uhe.

In *Ogba myth of origin* as noted by Ohia & Onyedibia in Ofili (2017), Akalaka was the founder of Ogba nation. He left Benin as a result of war. He prepared some charms which he placed on his bow arrows and when he shot, it directed him to the destination where he could find safety. When the arrow finally flew to the east, he and his followers prepared for eastward journey. The number of years it took Akalaka to get to the area cannot easily be estimated. When he arrived at Ogba, there were very few persons he displaced. Consequently, there are four major groups of kindred that make up Ogba community. These include Egi, Igburu, Omoku and Usominmi. It is pertinent to note that *Egwu otu* music is performed by the Omoku and Usomini kindreds of Ogba community. In the two kindred, as soon as a male child is old enough to socialize with others, he is made to familiarize with children of his age grade.

Historically, *Egwu otu* music originated from four fisher men, three hunters and two farmers. These nine men were members of Omoku and Usomini kindreds respectively. These men according to Pa Ojeadì (2016) in an oral interview, started this musical activity at a farm settlement which the Ogba people refer to as Ogbooru (plantation). These men usually come together every evening at the close of work after dinner to make music. This musical activity served as a means of relaxation and recreation to ease the day's stress. Apparently, the activity became interesting as the men realized that, they were of the same age bracket. As the performance continued, other men within the environment who had always listened to them with intense concentration indicated interest in the group and were accepted as members. Mr. Ibra (2016) in an oral interview said that this musical activity grew so strong that virtually all the men within the farm settlement became members of the group. However, women were not allowed to take part in this performance. After a year of this awesome activity, the oldest man amongst the group suggested that the performance should move beyond the farm settlement to their various towns where the membership will be thrown open to members of different age-grades. In other words, the musical activity should be recommended for every age-grade within the two kindreds (Omoku and Usomini) in Ogba land. The members of the group yielded to the old man's suggestion by splitting themselves in each community and formed different age grades and also introduced *Egwu Otu*. Membership was extended to the entire age-grades within the two kindreds. The emphasis with respect to the activity being exclusively for the menfolk of the community was strong and therefore, well adhered to by all age-grades. Men of two to three years' age brackets come together as an age grade.

The music involves Ogba traditional songs, accompanied with traditional music instruments and dancing. One of the significant roles of *Egwu otu* music is the bonding and socialization of members. The music is for entertainment. It is the only music in Ogba land used marking the end of the farming season, as well as ushering the community into a new year and a new farming season. The music plays a prominent role in rejuvenation, relaxation and entertainment. The songs have very simple melodious tunes in a call and response form. The dance movements are usually stylized and the members of the group dance in a uniform pattern.

It is pertinent to note that *Egwu Otu* musical performance usually hold between 26th to 31st December. The younger age grades between the ages of 8 to 15years observe their activities between 26th to 28th of December. The older ones from the ages of 16 to 39 observe theirs between 28th to 29th December, while the elders perform between 29th to 31st December, which is the grand finale. This last event involves long procession of all the older and elderly age grades round the entire community. The festival celebration is usually a glamorous one in terms of the attires used by each age-grade and performance. Every year each age-grade appear in different uniform as seen in pictures below:

Wives of “Otu Justice” Age Grade of Omoku with one of the researchers whose husband also belongs to the group dancing to a folk song

These are different age-grades in their different attires. If there are fifty (50) age-grades in the community, they appear in different uniforms during procession and at their various tents. This is the practice every year. It is pertinent to note that a particular uniform cannot be worn for two years. There is a change of uniform every year except for the death of a member of a particular age-grade. That particular age-grade will not make a new uniform that year, especially where the funeral of the deceased took place few months to the festival. This wonderful and entertaining display marks the end of the year.

Significance of *Egwu Otu* to Ogba Community

The historical background of *Egwu Otu* provides an insight to its significance to Ogba community under the following sub-headings;

1. Unification: It serves as a means of unification. This could be seen when the originators of *Egwu Otu* (the fisher men, hunters and farmers) usually come together to make music at the close of work for the day. These men were always looking forward to coming together every day. *Egwu Otu* attracted more members in the community who still uphold this particular tenet of togetherness even up to the present dispensation of post modernism.

2. Relaxation: *Egwu Otu* has created an avenue for members of the community to unwind. Business activities in the community involving individuals and groups are numerous and tend to wear them out. The music of *Egwu Otu* provides opportunity for members of the community to ease off their stress by singing, listening or dancing to the music. To buttress the statement above, Nketia in Olisake (2014) observes that;

In traditional African societies, music making is generally organized as a social event. Public performances therefore, take place on a social occasion-that is, on occasions when members of a group or community come together for the enjoyment of leisure, for recreational activities, or for any kind of collective activity, such as building bridges, clearing paths, going on a search party, or putting out fires –activities that in industrialized societies, might be assigned to specialized agencies. (p. 103)

Egwu Otu helps to get members of the community rejuvenated because at the point when the musical activity is on, they pay less attention to worries but are engrossed in the musical arts of *Egwu Otu*. The happy mood of community members involved in *Egwu Otu* affects their bodies, mind and health positively which makes them to be more energetic and productive in the next days' work. The songs used in the performances portray peace, harmony, love and also tell the end of the festive period. Some of the songs are also satirical in nature.

NWA LA KA EGO

Notated by
Doris Ofili & A.G. Albert

Solo

N wa n wa la ka'ego la'u wa n wa o n wa la ka'e go

5
la'u wa n wa o n wa la ka'e go la'u wa on ye ku la'e go'oyi

9
bo la ka nia n wa on ye ya ji si'e ego ozi ko jeo n wa la ka'e go

12
la'u wa

N.B. The melody above will be repeated as chorus.

DOFIL

Nwa la ka ego la uwa

Vernacular	English Version
<p><i>Nwa..nwa la ka ego la uwa (3x)</i> <i>Onye ku la ego onyibo la ka nia nwa</i> <i>Onye ya ji si ego ozi kwoje</i> <i>Nwa la ka ego la uwa.</i></p>	<p>Children are greater than money but whoever claims that dollar is greater than a child let the person send the dollar on an errand and see if the dollar will go.</p>

OKPARUKA OKUOJIO

Notators: Doris Ofili & Alfred Gelles Alfred

Call
O kpa rui ka o kuo jo ka nma la zu o

Response
kpa rui ka o kuo jo ka nma la zu e kwe la'i hu laon yi wee hu laon yi wee

hu laon yi wee o kpa rui ka o kuo jo ka nma la zuo

DOFIL

Okparuka

	Vernacular	English Version
Call:	<i>Okparuka oku ojuo ka nma la zuo</i> <i>Okparuka oku ojuo ka nma la zuo</i> <i>Umu uwa ihu la onye iwe</i>	Gossip is better in someone's absence Gossip is better in someone's absence The world, have you seen envious person
Response:	<i>E-ei...</i>	e-ei.. yes
Call:	<i>Ihu la onye iwe</i>	have you seen them...
Response:	<i>E..ei</i>	Gossip is better in someone's absence
Call:	<i>Ihu la onye iwe</i>	
All:	<i>Okparuka oku ojuo ka nma la zuo..</i>	

NDALA WIEMU MRE

Arrangers: Doris Oflili & Alfred Albert

Solo

Nda la wie mu mre ki bum'e
je.
Eze uwa ma.

DOFIL

Ndala wiemu mre

Vernacular	English Version
<p><i>Nda la wie mu mre ki bum'e je..?</i> <i>Nda la wie mu mre ki bum'e je?</i> <i>Eze uwa ma.</i></p>	<p>What have I done that you are carrying me around? What have I done that you are talking about me? King of better world.</p>

Emergence of Age-Grade Associations

Age grade associations came to be in Ogba community as a result of *Egwu Otu*. Members of the community through *Egwu Otu* are now abreast of those that are of the same age brackets as they come together to identify with a particular age grade. This has caused bonding to be at its peak amongst age grade members who do things in common and seek their common goals in the community.

Awareness of Important Dates

Egwu otu serves as an indicator or creates awareness of farming season and new year. It means that, there is a kind of music that will be heard in the community and (both old and young) members of Ogba community will be aware of the season being heralded.

Involvement in Exercise

People rarely engage in physical exercise on their own. The *Egwu Otu* dance music has created an avenue for members of the community to get involved in dance exercises in a stress-free manner accompanied by the music of *Egwu otu*. This is not to say that, some other activities do not help people in the community to exercise themselves. The emphasis is on stress-free manner. People go to farm and do some farm work which help them to exercise but it is not stress-free hence the emphasis on dancing to music. This in essence, has helped to keep members of the community fit and healthy thereby promoting healthy, living in the community to an extent.

Concept of Postmodern Performances

Postmodernism as stated in the Merriam Webster Dictionary (1983);

is a term relating to, or being an era after a modern one (postmodern times). It is also of relating to, or being any of various movements in reactions to modernism that are typically characterized by a return to traditional materials and forms (as in architecture) by ironic self-reference and absurdity as in literature.

More so, postmodernism;

is associated with relativism and a focus on the role of ideology in the maintenance of economic and political power. Postmodernists are skeptical explanations which claim to be valid for all groups. Cultures, traditions, or races, and instead focuses on the relative truth of each person. (<https://www.britannica.com>)

With respect to the definitions of modernism above, one thing is obvious, postmodernism is an antagony to modernism. An internet source opined that, modernism often embrace grand narratives and a belief in progress, rationality and the possibility of achieving universal truths. It aims for purity, simplicity and clarity in art, literature, and design. Postmodernism rejected grand narratives and the idea of a single objective truth. (<https://study.com.academy>)

Modernism believes that every culture should diversify and be progressive in nature and the progress should be collective and universal based. Modernism is also characterized with a rejection of traditional values and beliefs. On the other hand, postmodernism is characterized by self-reflexivity, inter-textuality, and a blurring of boundaries between high and low culture.

Apparently, postmodernism is subjective in their philosophy. In other words, the postmodernists believe in assumptions or feelings rather than facts. The philosophy of postmodernism is hinged on individuality of purpose, rather than the people's opinion. The aforementioned term is also characterized by skepticism which is an attitude of doubting the truth of something (such as a claim or statement). They believe that the doctrine, that truth is knowledge in a particular area, is uncertain. Most importantly, they also doubt the principles, values, and beliefs of various cultures and religions.

Furthermore, postmodernism is highly characterized by diversity. According to Merriam Webster Dictionary (1828) it is "the quality or state of having many different forms, types, ideas etc. It is also a state of having people who are of different races or who have different cultures in a group or organization". In other words, this factor actually allows for the integration of individuals into *Egwu Otu* group, irrespective of their race, tribe or culture. To buttress the above assertion, Vidal (2009) submits thus;

General studies tend to emphasize the more common traits or features of what we call African music which in actuality is the aggregate, not the sum total of all musical expressions which have

historical roots and origin in the soil of African but which also form a network of distinct yet related traditions which overlap in certain aspects of style, practice or usages (p. 1).

Implications of Postmodernism Performance of *Egwu otu* Activities

Considering the historical perspective and nature of *Egwu Otu* musical performance as stated earlier, it is one of the most significant cultural heritage which has been jealously upheld by the members of Omoku and Usomini communities in Ogba land. Every culture is meant to be for a people. Culture serves as a unique identity to every community. Therefore, no individual or few members of the community are expected to carry out any activity that is in contradiction to the culture of the people. Consequently, some aspects of postmodernism negatively impact on *Egwu Otu* musical activities. However, there are some positive impacts which postmodernism has on *Egwu Otu* dance music as well.

The negative impacts of postmodernism on *Egwu Otu* are below;

Subjectivity: humans are expected to be rational beings, not the other way round. It should not always be about someone's opinion or feelings but about existing beliefs of a people. With respect to the history of *Egwu Otu* on membership, women were not registered as members of age groups, rather, the married women and those that have attained marriageable age accompanied their spouses to their performances especially on the grand finale day. It adds a lot of color to the activity. Recently, some women joined various age grades as bonafide members. With this innovation, how will they accompany their husbands during the ceremony? This change came as a result of the selfish feelings of the women who believe that they are not treated as registered members. In addition, the young boys also take their girls as companion to their age-grades performances against the tradition. This is also born out of individuals feelings.

Another effect of postmodernism on *Egwu Otu* is the incorporating of popular dance movements, song texts and rhythms to the original ones. The elderly ones actually frowned at this because it does not align with the original practices. Besides this, the elderly ones lost admirers and spectators to the young age grade whose new innovations are attractive.

On the aspect of skepticism, it has negatively affected *Egwu Otu* as the younger ones are doubtful of the relevance of the cultural practice hence their embrace of popular practices thereby diluting the cultural beliefs and practices. This has given room to the youths behaving anyhow they feel like based on their individual perception.

Despite the negative aspect being discussed above, it is pertinent to also bring the positive effects of postmodernism to limelight. The positive effects are:

Innovations and Diversity: with respect to when the *Egwu Otu* dance musical performance started, there was no means of publicizing it. In recent times because of postmodernism, it has gained popularity via the social media platforms where the musical performances is easily projected and accessed. Some of the songs have also been recorded and preserved by some musicians of the community.

Furthermore, because of the exposure to watching other postmodern musical performances, members of *Egwu Otu* group incorporated uniform costumes in their attire which has added to the aesthetics of their dance performance. Going back to the inception of *Egwu Otu* dance music, members appeared in different attires during their performances.

FINDINGS

The researchers discovered that in recent times, *Egwu Otu* has undergone and is still undergoing some innovations which include:

1. Membership; as stated earlier, the founders of *Egwu Otu* dance music excluded the womenfolk from participating as members (that is joining an age grade of their choice), rather the women were expected to act as companions to their spouses, while attending the end of year activity. This was maintained till about four years ago when some of the women folk especially the younger ones started showing interest in joining their various age grades to participate as members. Interview with some members of the age grades revealed that, the sudden change does not go

down well with the founders of *Egwu Otu* as it contradicts the principles of *Egwu Otu*. Mr. Ike Ibra (2023) expressed his grievances over the new idea and sees it as a competition from the womenfolk.

Despite the expression of grievances by Mr. Ike Ibra, the researchers also found out that the men are to be blamed for the actions of the women. This is because, if they did not accept the women into the various groups, the women would not forcefully register themselves in the different groups. This in essence suggests that, the men are now compromising to the detriment of the original tenets of the groups. The men are to be blamed for the changes.

2. **Change of Days and Dates of Activities:** the study also discovered a serious change on the days of performance of the different age grades. The researchers earlier stated that *Egwu Otu* musical activities begin on the 26th -31st of every December. The younger boys between the ages of 8 to 15 years are the first to perform between 26th -28th at most while the youths start from the 28th to 30th. The older and elderly men begin on 29th or 30th to 31st of December which is the grand finale. Recently, this practice has started to dwindle as the youths are now in competition with the elderly men. The youths have taken to having their procession and performance on the same day slated for the elderly men. The older and elderly men also frown at this development.
3. In the aspect of the admission of women in the various age grades as members, the researchers discovered from interview with some of the women that it was mainly for fun. In other words, they want to belong and enjoy the fun that comes with the performances. These changes are mostly practiced by unmarried women and those who have not attained marriageable age.

Dance Steps and Song Texts

The researchers discovered that the Omoku youths have introduced western or popular dance steps and songs into their groups, and these innovations contradict the existing and laid down practices. Premised on the information, Okafor in Oguno and Nwamara (2014) posits that:

through song texts, a person learned moral codes of his land. He also learned about his language, the things his people lived by, and how the society worked. All these were learned through music that ranged from simple folk tunes to highly specialized ritual music, including chants, incantations and minstrelsy (116).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Egwu Otu dance music is the oldest and most common musical culture of the Omoku clan in Ogba community. Some of the norms and values of Ogba community are embedded in the dance music. Age grades evolved from *Egwu Otu* and encouraged bonding, and promoted good healthy living as a result of members of the community participates in stress-free dances. Postmodernism evolved and the younger ones embraced it by introducing popular music movements, song lyrics and practices which down-played the cultural practices to the annoyance of the founders of the group. Postmodernism also brought about new innovations and diversity in the manner the *Egwu Otu* is performed. Postmodernism has positive and negative impacts on *Egwu Otu* dance music.

Therefore the study recommends that, in as much as postmodernism has negative impact on *Egwu Otu* which the older menfolk of the community frown at. However the positive effects of postmodernism should not be overlooked. Irrespective of the innovations as a result of postmodernism, the youths should uphold the norms and values embedded in *Egwu Otu* musical performances which will in turn prevent the cultural practices of the community from going into extinction. The elders should accommodate the positive effects of postmodernism as this will enhance the advancement of *Egwu Otu* musical activities. It will also be pertinent for the youths of this community to be sanctioned for bringing their girlfriends to the age grade activities which is not the practice of the group.

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